

RECOGNITION OF SCIENTISTS IN THE HISTORY OF MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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Abstract: According to its original meaning, "management" means managerial activity. In a broad sense, it should be recognized that management has existed as a type of activity since the distant past of mankind. After all, people's living together ultimately leads to the establishment of certain socio-political and economic systems.

Key words: management, history, management system, concept.

According to many modern researchers, the emergence of the concept of "management" in the world of science is connected with the formation of market principles in the economic sphere. This scientific concept was mentioned for the first time at the end of the 20th century. According to its original meaning, "management" means managerial activity. In a broad sense, it should be recognized that management has existed as a type of activity since the distant past of mankind. After all, people's living together ultimately leads to the establishment of certain socio-political and economic systems. The formation of these different systems, in turn, stimulated the emergence of a special type of activity and social groups engaged in similar activities. Their work first developed on the basis of empirical practical experiences.

Each historical period had its own culture. It is reasonable to recognize that any cultural development is literally the generalized result of social experiences accumulated during social life.

The great scientists who became the honor of Uzbekistan created in all areas of

science that developed in their time and did great things. Their scientific potential and researches are very extensive. The scientist made very relevant and ancient comments on the management issues discussed by the fuzalos. That is why their advice is extremely valuable and useful for their contemporaries and future generations.

Abu Nasr Farabi (870 - 950) is one of these. Alloma's work called "The City of Virtuous People" contains very interesting ideas about management in a general sense. For example, the scientist thought about the conditions for ensuring the well-being of people's lives and said: "The well-being of social life depends first of all on the existence of a generous ruler. Such a ruler is a pledge of the celebration of justice in the country, as well as a person who cares for the needy. When talking about one of the important conditions of social well-being, this opinion of the scientist can be recognized: "A state based on uniting people with the intention of cooperation for good goals in social life is considered benevolent."

Farabi's advanced humanitarian ideas strongly influenced the formation of worldviews of another great genius from Central Asia. Abu Ali ibn Sina (980-1037) is more famous for his medical works. But Ibn Sina managed to write great works on other fields of science besides medicine. It is necessary to acknowledge his views on the principles of state management, in particular, the principles of ensuring a balance between state expenditures and revenues.

Abu Rayhan Beruni (973-1048), one of the contemporaries of Abu Ali ibn Sina, also made a special contribution to the advancement of science of his time. Focusing on Beruni's contribution to the development of modern socio-political sciences, the scientist reflects on the inextricable connection between man and the surrounding environment, the development and importance of relations between them, and the spiritual nature of man revealed the special place and role of labor in reaching maturity.

During the reign of the dynasty of Amir Temur (1336-1405) in Central Asia, many

branches of science, including modern economic sciences, were developed with extremely important teachings. and had a serious impact on its development. This ruler managed to create a specially designed political system to manage his enormous kingdom.

Along with the formation and development of the field of political management, a system of views compatible with management ideas has also been developed, which cannot be denied. The views of the ruler in the field of political management are mainly expressed clearly in the work called "The Laws of Timur".

The further development of advanced management ideas, which motivated the creation of management, can be observed while studying the works of Alisher Navoi (1441-1501), one of the scholars of the East. Alisher Navoi, a great poet, thinker and statesman, expressed his economic and political views in 22 works. In the works "Zakaria" and "Munshaot" Alisher Navoi expresses his valuable thoughts about the socio-economic structure of the society.

Abdurrahman Jami (1414-1492), Zahiriddin Muhamad Babur (1483-1530), Mirzo Bedil (1644-1721), Azodi (1700-1760), Mahtumquli (1733-1782) and other geniuses cannot be forgotten.

The development of modern science was influenced by Eastern and Western thinkers in their own way.

In the East, the spiritual search and elevation of man is considered the main goal, while in the West, the search for the freedom and spiritual elevation of the whole humanity is considered important. Therefore, it is possible that the ability of Eastern thinkers to directly apply theological and theoretical knowledge to practice is limited due to some objective conditions. Such opportunities and practical experiences were realized in Western countries.

For the first time in the history of mankind, a set of laws on labor in factory conditions was developed in Great Britain. Later, such works were carried out in

countries such as Germany, France, and Austria. It should be emphasized here that the advanced ideas about social guarantees described in the works of Eastern scholars were reflected in the recognized legal systems. . However, the Western reformers approached this issue in their own way, besides, the socio-political and economic development of the Western countries developed differently from that of the Eastern countries. This uniqueness ultimately determines the course of events and the solution of problems. According to the historical development tradition of Eastern countries, the implementation of reforms in social and political life and the protection of citizens' interests are entrusted to the state (ruler). Accordingly, the masses lived with hope.

In Western countries, these processes took place under the background of sharp class struggles. The public and the individual were inclined to show personal activity in order to protect their interests. As a result of uncompromising struggles (socio-economic conflict) between those who exploit the power of hired workers and hired workers, reforms have taken place in the entire social structure. It is extremely gratifying that the conditions observed at the heart of such political processes and the measures to eliminate the conflicts based on them have been expressed in one way or another in the works of Eastern thinkers.

In the West, it was recognized that the achievement of human perfection was realized through intelligence (pragmatism). And intelligence seeks to understand the essence of everything, to determine the driving forces of processes, to organize all the elements of the structure in a certain way.

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